

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Aduloju****FIRST NAME: Gbemisola****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. Laurent Cleenewerck/ Dr. Kabiru Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did not use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: MS Word 2007

GUIDING PRINCIPLE FOR PROFESSIONAL AND ACADEMIC WRITING USING EUCLID AS A CASE STUDY

1) INTRODUCTION

In my way of studying the International Academic and Professional Paper Writing Courses, in ACA 401/ACA – 401D coursepack pack Period One (1), I have observed that the information in the coursepack period one, provides a few tips, to keep in mind, while composing professional documents. The comprehensive writing manual for students and 14 minutes video are good source of guiding principles for excellent professional and academic writing. This course gives an awareness into EUCLID's expectations on how to, write, edit, and present my response and major papers. In this response paper, I will address the coursepack as follows: essay writing, style, structure, plagiarism and lastly the 14 minutes video.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The first topic I read in the ACA-401 coursepack is essay writing. As part of my professional employment, I have written essays, articles and other documents, for many years. However, the course materials offered a refreshing viewpoint on writing. The basics steps in writing an essay is sequential as seen in the manual is to first analyze the question and define key terms, establish a possible thesis, research the topic by using credible academic sources for support and evidence, taking notes from readings, write an essay plan and organize ideas and write first draft (EUCLID 2015, 2).

The tips for effective writing as outlined in the coursepack is to work on writing the first draft on time to avoid anxiety and give time to develop ideas. However, it is necessary not to write an essay from beginning to end. When writing a paper, it is advisable to start with an introduction that gives the reader a clear map of what to expect from the beginning of the paper to the end. It is also important to always outline the paragraphs before writing to make sure thoughts flow logically from one to the next and make sure each paragraph starts with a thesis statement or a topic sentence that lets the reader know what the topic for the next paragraph will be (EUCLID 2015, 3).

The rules of thumb for writing papers on the coursepack simplifies some suggestions about writing professional papers (EUCLID 2015, 43 – 45). The review of LIT 101 on Grammar is also a revelation as it highlights grammatical errors to avoid when writing Academic Papers.

However, it is worth mentioning that consistency is a key characteristic in academic writing, the coursepack enlightens me to pay attention to choose a language and not to diverge from it in order to be coherent. It also gives so much insight into differences between British and American English and punctuation. It is worth revealing that the coursepack captured many different style aspects like font usage, ideal sentence length, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology and how in text and bibliography should be used in response and major papers.

The CMS Crib Sheet by Dr. Abel Scribe Ph.D. attached in the coursepack simplifies and explains the rules related to abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, italics, and quotation marks, numbers as well as the Chicago page formats and Chicago endnotes and footnotes when writing Academic and Professional Paper (EUCLID 2015, 66).

3) STYLE

A good academic paper includes the right set of style that is suitable for the content. A Lawyer is expected to use the Bluebook. The same specifiers of styles go for the health specialists who can make proper usage of the WHO rule of style. Therefore, the rule of style is a symbol of uniqueness.

The academic writing styles is formal unless instructed as per the EUCLID coursepack in respect to the response papers where the use of personal pronouns like ‘I’ and ‘me’ for example are accepted and should avoid contracted word such as “don’t” and be in plain English as much as possible. However, some Latin expressions can be accepted for example when an original ‘misused’ word has been accurately quoted, the Latin term ‘(sic)’ is used to emphasize the term and signal to the reader that the word is cited faithfully. The aim of using plain English is to provide the full clarity and to avoid any misunderstanding (EUCLID 2015, 43).

4) STRUCTURE

In EUCLID context, structure of a good paper is to communicate ideas and answer the question. Furthermore, the coursepack explains how a structured good essay is outlined as follows: introduction, body, and conclusion. On the other hand, it is essential to point out that paragraphing is preceded by an introduction and sealed by the conclusion (EUCLID 2015, 4).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism occurs when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the Author of that source of information (EUCLID 2015, 9). The avoidance of acknowledging other people's work is counterproductive and unethical. I strongly support EUCLID's clear direction not to accept plagiarism.

The course material provides simple guides on how to avoid Plagiarism as follows: Citations in-text and end-text citations, quotations, and paraphrasing.

a) Citations

Citation is the method used to indicate where a piece of information came from. There are two types of citations, In-text citations and end-text citations. In text citations are made within the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself. Quotations and Paraphrases are some of the more common things we normally cite using in-text citation method. (EUCLID 2015, 16) while end text citations are found at the end of paraphrased sentence of quotation.

b) Quotations

Quotations are the exact words of an author. It is always important to use quotation marks when use a quotation to capture the words of the author, however, another important point to note is that quotations that are over four lines will be treated differently, as they will have no quotation marks and indented to look like a little paragraph (EUCLID 2015, 19).

c) Paraphrasing

Paraphrasing shows an idea and information that an author has produced the knowledge, which another author has created. One of the techniques for paraphrasing is not only to change few words but rather use own words to describe the message, it is also recommended that the writing style should be different from the style the author used. (EUCLID 2015, 23)

However, the 14-minute video presentation by Professor Cleenewerck, demonstrated how to understand templates, styles, file naming methods, and the difference between a rule of style and a heading or paragraph style in a simple manner.

6) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the course covered a significant number of important topics, including essay writing, rule of style, Turabian grammar and formatting, basic differences between American and British English as well as how to use Latin abbreviations and expressions. Authentication in academic work is very important and how to avoid plagiarism has been highlighted and how it can be avoided by using citation, quotation, or paraphrasing, and listing the references at the end of the document using reference manager software to keep the list uniform has been streamlined. This is achieved thoroughly by using Zotero reference manager.

I have spent so much time to read and analyze the coursepack and watch the video. The video has taught me how to correct lots of flaws that are common in my ways of writing before I started ACA-401 Course.

I look forward to keep on using ACA-401 coursepack materials and video as a guiding principle for professional and academic writing, throughout the course and in my career, to help me become a better writer. I believe the tools in ACA-401 will help me build up my skills on how to write professionally and efficiently.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. ACA-401 coursepack: Period 1. Retrieved from:
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<http://vimeo.com.157480457>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.